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ENFORCEMENT OF ARBITRATION AGREEMENT UNDER THE ARBITRATION AND MEDIATION ACT 2023 – STAY OF PROCEEDINGS: KWARA STATE GOVERNMENT & ORS V. GUTHRIE NIG. LTD (2023)34 WRN 1 (2022)13NWLR (Pt.1846)189 A REVISIT

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Abstract: In this research we are concerned with arbitration agreement under the Act. Arbitration is said to be under the Act if the arbitration agreement is in writing within the provisions of section 2 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023. Arbitration is the reference of a dispute or difference or differences between not less than two parties for determination, after hearing both sides in a judicial manner, by a person or persons other than a court of competent jurisdiction which renders a decision called award.¹ Arbitral award is a judgment. Where a party after entering into an arbitration agreement reverts to court on the occurrence of the dispute rather than reverting to arbitration in accordance with their agreement, the party aggrieved by the breach of the arbitration agreement is not without a remedy. The question which may be asked is what is the remedy of the aggrieved party? Does this remedy apply to all arbitration agreement or a specific form of arbitration agreement? A party who is aggrieved that the recalcitrant party has reverted to court instead of going to arbitration as agreed by the parties has a right to apply for stay of proceedings to the court where the matter is pending. Is it in all arbitration agreement that application for stay will apply? What are the principles guiding the granting of stay of proceedings in arbitration matter? Does filing of notice of intention to defend in an undefended List proceeding constitute a step in the proceedings within the provision of section 5 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 which is *impair materia* with section 5 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act 2004. It is to answer these questions that we have embarked on this research.

Keywords: Enforcement, Arbitration Agreement, Arbitration and Mediation Act, Stay of Proceedings.

1. Introduction

Arbitration is a form of ADR, which is alternative dispute resolution method. ADR is generally used to describe the methods and procedures used to resolve disputes either as alternatives to the traditional dispute

¹ Halsbury's Laws of England 3rd Ed. 38. *N.N.P.C. v. Lutin Investment Ltd.* (2006) NSCQR 77.

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resolution mechanism of the court or in some cases as supplementary to such mechanism.² Arbitration is an agreement of the parties that a dispute between them be settled by a tribunal of their choice.³ In *Collins v. Collins*⁴ the court defined arbitration as a reference to the decision of one or more persons either with or without an umpire, of a particular matter in difference between the parties. Halsbury's Laws of England defined arbitration as the reference of a dispute or differences or difference between not less than two parties for determination, after hearing both sides in a judicial manner, by a person or persons other than a court of competent jurisdiction.⁵ Russell defined arbitration to mean "a written agreement to submit a present or future difference to arbitration whether an arbitrator is named therein or not."⁶ Section 91(1) defined arbitration as a commercial arbitration whether or not administered by a permanent arbitral institution.⁷

As stated earlier in this work, we are concerned with arbitration under the Act in this research paper. Arbitration is said to be under the Act if the agreement is reduced into writing in accordance with the Act. Arbitration agreement may be in the form of an arbitration clause in a contract or in the form of a separate complete agreement. Section 2 (1)(2)&(3) provides that the agreement shall be in writing where its content is recorded in any form, whether or not the arbitration agreement or contract has been concluded orally, by conduct, or by any other means.⁸ The requirement for arbitration agreement to be in writing is met, where it is-

- (a) By an electronic communication, as defined in section 91, and the information contained in it is accessible so as to be useable for subsequent reference; and
- (b) it is contained in an exchange of point of claim and defence in which the existence of an agreement is alleged by one party and not denied by the other.⁹

It is important to state that a reference in a contract or a separate arbitration agreement to a document containing an arbitration clause constitutes an arbitration agreement in writing, provided that the reference is in such manner that makes it part of the contract or the arbitration agreement.¹⁰

Who is an arbitrator? An arbitrator is a third neutral and unbiased umpire to who disputes are referred to by the parties. He is an independent person or body officially appointed to settle a dispute. He is an impartial, neutral third party selected or appointed by disputing parties to hear evidence, review testimony and render a final and legally binding decision known as an award which resolves their conflict outside of a traditional court system. Section 91(1) of the Act defined arbitrator to mean a person to whom a reference is made for determination and includes substitute or emergency arbitrator.

We have two types of commercial arbitration, that is, domestic and international commercial arbitration. We also have different forms of domestic commercial arbitration namely, customary law arbitration, common law arbitration, and arbitration under the Act. Stay of proceedings as a means of enforcement of arbitration agreement only applies to arbitration under the Act as it is provided for in section 5 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023. The only thing that is common to the three forms of domestic arbitration agreement is that

² Orojo J. O. & Ajomo M. A., *Law and Practice of Arbitration and Conciliation in Nigeria*, Mbeyi & Associates Nig. Ltd, Lagos, 1999, 4

³ Ronald Bernstein, *Handbook of Arbitration Practice*, 8.

⁴ 28LJCH 186

⁵ *Halsbury's Laws of England*, 3rd Ed. 38. *N.N.P.C. v. Lutin Investment Ltd.*(2006)NSCQR77at 112.

⁶ Russell on Arbitration 18th Ed. 38.

⁷ Section 91(1) Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

⁸ Section 2(1)(2)(3) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

⁹ Section 2 (4) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

¹⁰ Section 2(5) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

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agreement is the centre of gravity in all the three. This means that the legal basis of the three forms of domestic arbitration is agreement but as written agreement is the requirement of arbitration agreement under the Act, oral agreement governs the customary and common law arbitration.

2. Remedies for the Breach of Arbitration Agreement.

Where parties entered into arbitration agreement, it is expected that on the occurrence of disputes or difference in the contract, the dispute(s) will be referred to the arbitrators for determination. Unfortunately, this is not always the case. There exist situations wherein on the occurrence of dispute within the contractual terms of the parties who had agreed to refer matters to arbitration, a recalcitrant party reverts to court instead of first referring the matter to arbitration in accordance with the terms of their agreement. Under the common law and customary law arbitration, the other party who is aggrieved that a subject matter of arbitration agreement has been taken to court is helpless as he cannot apply for stay of proceedings though he can sue for action at law for breach of contract to arbitrate. Under the Act, the aggrieved party is accorded a remedy of application for stay of proceedings pursuant to section 5(1) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act.

A person who is a party to the arbitration agreement under the Act cannot suffer breach of agreement to go without remedy. One of the remedies is as provided in section 5(1) of the Act which provides that-

Notwithstanding the provision of any other law, a court before which an action is brought in a matter, which is the subject of arbitration agreement shall, if any of the parties request, not later than when submitting their first statement on the substance of the dispute, refer the parties to arbitration unless it finds that the agreement is void, inoperative or incapable of being performed.

The court before which the matter which is the subject matter of arbitration is brought has a duty to stay proceedings and refer the parties to arbitration on the premise that failure to do so will give impetus to the party which is in breach in continuing with his action. It is the duty of the court to ensure that the parties keep to the terms of their agreement. In *Hallam v. Attorney General of Plateau State*,¹¹ the court stated that “where an agreement made by the parties stipulates that any dispute arising therefrom must first be referred to a referee, it would amount to jumping the queue for any of the parties to resolve to go to the court first before the dispute between the parties is referred to an appointed referee.” The court in *Commerce Assurance Ltd v. Alli* decided among others that “compliance with the agreement of the parties by going to arbitration is a condition to be observed before the commencement of any action in court.”¹² However, for the court to intervene or make any order with respect to any matter commenced in court in breach of arbitration agreement, the arbitration clause or the terms of the arbitration agreement must be mandatory, precise and unequivocal.¹³

It is not always that where application for stay is made the court would grant stay of proceedings. The court has the discretion to grant or refuse the granting of the application. This is because the Act provided basis pursuant to which the application could be granted. The application would be refused if the court finds out that the arbitration agreement is void, inoperative or incapable of being performed. In nutshell, the court will also not enforce the arbitration agreement or grant stay of proceedings if the agreement was obtained by fraud, undue influence or by misrepresentation. The court will also not grant the application for stay if the party applying for the stay has taking a step in the proceedings before the court. What constitutes taking a step for the provisions

¹¹ (1996)9NWLR (Pt.471)242 at 249.

¹² (1992)3NWLR (Pt. 232)701 at 702

¹³ *Bebeji Oil Allied Prod. Ltd & Anor. V. Pancostal Ltd* (2007)31 WRN 163 at 173.

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of section 5 of the Act? In *Hasting v. Nigeria Railway Corporation*,¹⁴ Taylor, C.J., held that the defendant who sought an order for pleadings had taken a step in the proceedings. In *Kano State Urban Development Board (KSUD) v. Fanz Construction Co. Ltd.*¹⁵ Ogundare J.C.A. held that the following acts constitute taking a step in the proceedings, that is:-

- i. Seeking an extension of time within which to file a statement of defence¹⁶
- ii. Taking out a summons for directions or something of that kind
- iii. Attendance and taking part at the hearing of summons for directions
- iv. Seeking an order for pleadings.

Taken a step in the proceedings means taking concrete actions in pursuit or furtherance of the suit in the court filed in breach of arbitration agreement. Mere talk between solicitors or letter for adjournment cannot amount to taking a step.¹⁷ Entering appearance whether conditional or unconditional does not also amount to taking a step.¹⁸ A party who had taken a step in the proceedings before applying for stay will fail in his application because having taken a step in the proceedings, he is deemed to have waived his right to complained.

Another remedy open to the aggrieved party whose arbitration agreement had been breached is to seek for the order of specific performance from the court. Some scholars have argued and courts decided that the order of specific performance of an arbitration agreement can be made by the court. With respect and humility, this is not right because order of specific performance which is an equitable remedy applies in cases where the award of damages cannot be sufficient remedy particularly in contract under seal. Award of damages can adequately compensate for any injury which the defendant will suffer for the breach of arbitration agreement. Secondly, arbitration agreement whether or not is contained in an independent contract or as a clause in an agreement under seal, remains a simple contract. In *Royal Exchange Assurance v. Bentworth Finance Nig. Ltd.*¹⁹ the Supreme Court decided that the court has, not only the power and jurisdiction to appoint arbitrator on an application properly made by the other party who has served such notice, but also to decree a specific performance of the arbitration agreement. Also in *T. A. Hammond Project v. Federal Housing Authority*,²⁰ the court held that “it is ideal to say that no court makes a contract for the parties but once they have of their own free will made a contract for themselves and it is before the court, the court would hold them bound to the terms agreed upon between them, unless it is illegal and/or unreasonable.”

A party whose arbitration agreement had been breached can treat same as a breach of contract. A party to the arbitration agreement has a right to treat the act of reverting to court instead of arbitration by the recalcitrant party as a breach of agreement by seeking for common law remedy of action at law for breach of contract. In this case, the defendant in the matter in court waives his right of going to arbitration but seeks for redress for breach of the arbitration agreement. The aggrieved party will be required to file his writ of summons and serve the defendant with all the necessary document of front loading including his statement on oath. He will urge the court to award damages for the breach of the arbitration agreement he had entered with the plaintiff who took

¹⁴ (1964)LLR. 135

¹⁵ (1986)5NWLR (Pt.39)1

¹⁶ *Obemba v. Wemabod Estate* (1977)5 SC 115 at 131.

¹⁷ *United World Ltd. V. M.T.S. Ltd.* (1998)10NWLR (Pt568)106.

¹⁸ *Confidence Insurance Ltd v. Trustees of OSCE.* (1998)2 NWLR (Pt.591) 373 at 387. See also the cases of *Onward Ent. V. MV"Matrix" & Zors* (2009)4WRN 103 at 109. *Jadesimi v. Egbe & Ors* (2003)36WRN79.

¹⁹ (1976)6UILR (Pt.2)293.

²⁰ (1977)CCHCJ 2467 at 2468.

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the matter which is subject of arbitration clause to court. The three remedies available to a party whose arbitration agreement had been breach are the application for stay of proceedings, the order for specific performance by the court, and action at law for breach of simple contract. However, the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 made provision for only application for stay of proceedings.²¹

3. The Facts and History of the Case

The respondent commenced an action at the High Court of Kwara State (hereinafter simply referred to as “the trial court”) by way of writ of summons under the undefended list procedure against the appellants. It claimed for the payment of the sum of N586,206,883.33 as money due to it. Upon being served with the writ of summons and accompanying affidavit, the appellants joined issues with the respondent by filing a notice of intention to defend together with a supporting affidavit. **They urged the trial court to transfer the suit to the general list for hearing on the merits. The appellants, simultaneously, raised a preliminary objection to the hearing of the suit. They pray the court to strike the suit for want of jurisdiction or stay proceedings thereon, and refer the matter to arbitration.** They drew the trial court’s attention to the existence of arbitration clause in the agreement between the parties. In response, the respondent filed a counter –affidavit in opposition to this application.

The trial court, by its ruling delivered on March 23, 2017, upheld the appellant’s preliminary objection, thereby declining jurisdiction. It referred the suit to arbitration. Dissatisfied with the ruling of the trial court, the respondent appealed to the lower court via a notice of appeal filed on April 20, 2017, containing four grounds of appeal. In its judgment, delivered on November 20, 2017, the lower court, unanimously, allowed the appeal and set aside the decision of the trial court. The lower court then ordered that the suit be remitted to the trial court for a rehearing by another judge. Dissatisfied, the appellants then appealed to the Supreme Court.²²

4. Decision of the Supreme Court

The Supreme Court considered a lot of issues in this matter before making a final decision in the matter. We will then revert to the issues considered. The Court considered that this matter arose out of undefended list matter where what is required is that the appellant has to file a notice of intention to defend and not memorandum of appearance. The Court reasoned that the undefended list procedure is indeed special and unique and all that the defendant to it is required to do is to file a notice of intention to defend with its accompanying affidavit which must disclose a triable issue. As this is a special procedure provided specifically by the law and rule court, a party is bound to commence the action in the way prescribed, and the court is bound to give enforcement to it.²³The court contended that even if the defendant had filed a statement of defence, same would have been set aside as not proper.²⁴The Court then held that:

Where parties to a contract have, under the terms thereof, agreed to submit to arbitration if there is any dispute arising from the contract between them, a defendant who has not taken any steps in the proceedings commenced by the other party, may apply to the court for a stay of proceedings of the action, to enable the parties go to arbitration as contracted. In the instant case, the appellants’ act of filing of a notice of intention to

²¹ Section 5 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

²² *Kwara State Govt. & Ors v. Guthrie Nig. Ltd.* (2022)34WRN 1 at 3

²³ *Ifezue v. Mbadugha* (1984)1SCNLR 427. *Dangote v. Civil Service Commission Plateau State* (2001)9 NWLR (Pt.717)132.

²⁴ *Nishizawa Ltd. V. Jethwani* (2001)8 WRN 153.

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defend did not amount to taking a step in the proceeding, contrary to section 5 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act.²⁵

The Supreme Court held this view because according to the Order 23 Rule 3(1) of the High Court Rules of Kwara State (Civil Procedure) Rules, 2005, a defendant on whom a writ of summons and affidavit is served under the undefended list procedure is required not less than 5 days before the day fixed for hearing, to file a notice in writing that he intends to defend the suit, together with an affidavit disclosing a defence on the merit. Sequel to this, the court may give him leave to defend and transfer the suit to general cause list and may order pleadings or proceed to hearing without further pleading. According to the court, it is mandatory for the defendant to file a notice of intention to defend without more as doing otherwise will amount to non-compliance.²⁶

5. Discussion/Commentary

The law is well spelt out that a party to arbitration agreement has a duty to revert to arbitration on the occurrence of any dispute in the contract. Where a party reverts to court without first referring their dispute to arbitration in accordance with the terms of their agreement, an aggrieved party who is a party to the agreement has a right to apply for stay of proceedings to the court. The Court has a duty to order for stay of proceedings if the party applying for stay has not taken any step in the proceedings before the court.²⁷ Before the court can grant or decline the application for stay pursuant to section 5(1) of the Act, the arbitration clause must be mandatory, precise and unequivocal.²⁸ In *Hallam v. Attorney General of Plateau State*,²⁹ the court decided that, “where an agreement made by the parties stipulates that any dispute arising therefrom must first be referred to a referee, it would amount to jumping the queue for any of the parties to resolve to go to the court first before the dispute between the parties is referred to an appointed referee.” Only parties to the arbitration agreement or any person claiming through them or their accredited representatives with their consent and authority has right to apply for stay of proceedings. Sequel to the provisions of section 5 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act, once the application is right on the face of it, that is, if the applicant applies for the stay before taken step in the proceedings, the court has only one duty to perform and that duty is to grant stay of proceedings unless where the court finds out that the agreement is void, inoperative or incapable of being performed. The court has a mandatory duty to grant stay where the arbitration agreement is voluntary, valid, proper in law and unequivocal. It is even more mandatory in a situation where the applicant was at the time when the action was commenced ready to go on arbitration and has done everything on his own part to ensure that arbitration takes place.

In *Kwara State Government & 20rs v. Guthrie Nig. Ltd.*,³⁰ which is the case of our main concern in this research, the Supreme Court, decided that filing of a notice of intention to defend did not amount to taking a step in the proceedings. It is very important to state that the Supreme Court failed to consider certain important

²⁵ *Kwara State Govt & Ors v. Guthrie Nig. Ltd.* (2022)34WRN 1 at 12 (2022)13NWLR(Pt.1846) 189 at 194). *Owners of MV Lupex v. Nigerian Overseas Chartering and Shipping Ltd.* (2003)15NWLR (Pt.844)469. *Sakamori Const. Nig. Ltd v. Lagos State Water Corporation* (2022)5NWLR (Pt. 1823)339. *Obemba v. Wemabod Esates Ltd* (1977)5SC 115.

²⁶ *Nishizawa Ltd. v. Jethwani* (2001)8 WRN 153.

²⁷ Section 5 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

²⁸ *Bebeji Oil Allied Prod. Ltd. & Anor v. Pancostal Ltd.* (2007)31WRN 163 at 173

²⁹ *Ibidi. Commerce Assurance Ltd. V. Alli* (1992)3NWLR(Pt.232)701. *Mbeledogu v. Aneto* (1996)2NWLR (Pt.429)157. *UBA Plc v. Triedent Consult. Ltd.* (2023)33WRN 1. *Fawehinmi Construction Co. Ltd. V. OAU* (1998)6NWLR (Pt.553)171.

³⁰ *Kwara State Govt. & 20rs v. Kuthrie Nig. Ltd. (supra)* 189.

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issues in this matter before making their final decision. The court distinguished the case of *Obembe v. Wemabod Estate*³¹ on the premise that the writ in *Kwara State Govt & 2Ors v. Guthrie Nig. Ltd.*³² was under the undefended list procedure in accordance with Order 23 Rule 3(1) of the Kwara State High Court (Civil Procedure) Rules of 2005 whereas the case of *Obembe* was commenced by ordinary writ of summons. The most important thing to mention is that taking a step means taking a step whether the matter was commenced by ordinary writ of summons or by undefended list procedure. We agree completely with the Court of Appeal in its decision that filing of notice of intention to defend is a form of defence to the suit filed under the undefended list procedure.

The only thing that one could say that saved the day in this matter was the fact of including a preliminary object in the same notice of intention to defend. It was very unfortunate that the Supreme Court did not distinguish a situation where a party filed a notice of intention to defend including in it a preliminary objection challenging the jurisdiction of the court for reason of arbitration clause in the contract, and where what was filed was a mere notice of intention to defend. Where preliminary objection challenging the jurisdiction of the court for reasons of the arbitration clause pursuant to section 5 of the Act was included in the notice of intention to defend, one could say that the appellants though had filed notice of intention to defend but were consistently and continuously praying and urging the court to grant stay of proceedings because of the arbitration agreement entered into by the parties. A party who intends to filing application for stay ought to comply with the provisions of section 5 of the Act which requires that the applicant shall filed a motion on notice praying the court to grant him stay of proceedings. Filing a notice of intention to defend and including therein a preliminary objection is a wrong approach but pressing hard on this may amount to unnecessary technicality. Filing of notice of intention to defend under the undefended list procedure amounts to taking a step within the provisions of section 5 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act.

What is taking a step in the proceeding so as to determine if the Supreme Court was right in this matter? Taking a step means any step a party takes in furtherance of the proceedings in the court. For a clearer picture of the meaning of taking a step, we have to also refer to *K.S.U.D.B. v. Fanz Construction Co. Ltd*³³ where Ogundare, JCA, held that the following acts constitute taking a step in the proceedings, that is:

- i. Seeking an extension of time within which to file a statement of defence.³⁴
- ii. Taking out summons for directions or something of that kind
- iii. Attendance and taking part at the hearing of summons for directions.
- iv. Seeking an order for pleadings.

Sequel to the decision of the court in *K.S.U.D.B. v. Fanz*, a step in the proceedings means some concrete action taken in pursuit or furtherance of a suit in court and not mere talk between solicitors or solicitors' clerks or writing of letters. There must be a step taken such as taking out summons.³⁵ If all these constitute taking a step, why must filing of notice of intention to defend not amount to taking a step. This is because the essence of filing a notice of intention to defended in undefended list proceeding is to enable the party who is desirous to

³¹ (1977)LPELR 2161

³² *ibid*

³³ (1986)5 NWLR (Pt.39)1

³⁴ *Obembe v. Wemabod Estate* (1977)5 SC 115 at 131.

³⁵ *Ives & Baker v. Williams* (1894)2CH. 77. *United World Ltd Inc. v. M.T.S. Ltd.* (1998)10NWLR (Pt.568)106 *Confidence Insurance Ltd. V. Trustees of Ondo State Collegde of Education Staff Pension* (1999)2NWLR (Pt.591)373.

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defend present a notice accompanied by an affidavit showing that he has a defence to the matter. It is a form of defence to action under undefended suit. Where he succeeds, the matter will be transferred to the general cause list. It is a step taken in furtherance of the suit filed by the plaintiff in a case of liquidated money sum where the plaintiff is claiming that the defendant has no defence to the claim before the court. The action taken by the defendant who has filed a notice of intention to defend is to demonstrate that he has a credible defence in the matter. The implication of that action is that the notice of intention to defend is a defence to the undefended list matter filed by the plaintiff hence it is a step in the proceedings. Filing of memorandum of appearance whether conditional or otherwise is not a step in the proceedings. Achike JCA in *Confidence Insurance Ltd. V. Trustees of OSCE*³⁶ decided thus:

It is perfectly clear to me that mere entering an appearance by the appellant be it conditional or unconditional appearance is not controlling nor relevant to the party's right to rely on the arbitration clause inserted in the parties agreement. On the contrary, it is in fact what happens after a party has entered an appearance that matters in determining whether or not such a party can still take advantage of the aforesaid arbitration clause. With humility and respect, the Supreme Court is obviously in error in their decision in this matter of *Kwara State Government v. Kuthrie*. It is expected that the court will in due course reverse its decision in this matter.

Conclusion

The principle of stay of proceedings pursuant to section 5 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act is to save arbitration practice and give effect to the arbitration agreement of the parties. The court has a duty to ensure that parties keep to the terms of their arbitration agreement hence the decision of the court in *Kano State Urban Development Board v. Fanz Construction Co. Ltd*³⁷ wherein the court decided that parties must not be allowed to jump the queue. It is for this reason that where the arbitration agreement is valid, unequivocal, and capable of being performed, the court will grant stay of proceedings so as to enable the parties exhaust the terms of their agreement. To allow or give parties the opportunity of abandoning their arbitration agreement and reverting to court on the occurrence of dispute which is subject matter of arbitration, will make nonsense of arbitration practice. In granting application for stay of proceedings, the court has discretion either to grant or refuse the application based on the provisions of section 5 of the Act. Having seriously considered the provisions of section 5 of the Act and all other previous decisions of courts in Nigeria and beyond, we are respectfully of the opinion that the Supreme Court decision in *Kwara State Government & 2Ors v. Guthrie Nig Ltd*³⁸ was wrong in law. It is expected that the Supreme Court will reverse this decision in future.

³⁶ *ibidi*

³⁷ *K.S.U.D.B. v. Fanz Construction Co Ltd (supra)*¹

³⁸ (2022)34WRN 1.